

DWT-SVD Technique for Audio Watermarking Color Image

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Abstract: The rapid growth of digital media and communication network has highlighted the need for Intellectual Property Rights (IRP) protection technology for digital multimedia. Watermarking can be used to identify the owners, license information, or other information related to the digital object carrying the watermark. Watermarks can provide the mechanism for determining if a particular work has been tampered with or copied illegally. The embedded information that is inserted in the cover-signal, is referred to as the payload or watermark. The digital watermark encoded into digital data is an identifying code and may consist of a bit sequence, random numbers, text representing user's unique ID or copyright ownership message or Cryptographic keys or access conditions of the content, logos, image, biometrics or content-based information.

In this project, an algorithm is proposed for robust audio watermarking in color images using DWT-SVD. Here a color image is used as a cover by the fact that human visual system is less sensitive than human auditory system thus a color image provides better masking effect. The algorithm is based on decomposition of color images using DWT-SCVD. The hidden data can be recovered reliably under certain attacks such as cropping, compression, noise effect, geometrical attacks and contrast enhancement.

Keywords: Audio Watermarking, Discrete wavelet Transform, Communication Network, Digital Media, Singular Value Decomposition.

1.Introduction

The use of Internet as a platform for distribution of digital media has grown in recent years causing serious concerns about unauthorized use and manipulation of digital contents. Digital media offer several distinct advantages over analog media, such as high quality, easy editing, higher ease of copying etc. Digital content such as Images, video files, audio files, etc., are prone to being accidentally or maliciously modified, altered or destroyed by un-authorized subjects. Many advantages of digital information has also generated new challenges and new opportunities for innovation in this domain. Along with powerful software, new devices, such as digital camera and camcorder, high quality scanners and printers, digital voice recorder, have reached consumers worldwide to create, manipulate, and enjoy the available data in accordance to their requirements. To deal with the issue of data integrity, authentication techniques are required to verify correctness and validity of the digital content.

Based on the provision of authenticity to the digital information, various approaches are developed to ensure data hiding. The data hiding refers to embedding a secondary digital data (Secret Information) into the primary data (Host). To achieve this various security approaches such as cryptography, steganography and watermarking etc., were developed.

Watermarking, as opposed to steganography, has an additional requirement of robustness against possible attacks. An ideal Steganographic system would embed a large amount of information

perfectly securely, with no visible degradation to the host object. An ideal watermarking system, however, would embed an amount of information that could not be removed or altered without making the host object entirely unusable. As a side effect of these different requirements, a watermarking system will often trade capacity and perhaps even some security for additional robustness.

1.1 Digital Watermarking: Digital watermarking, is a field that refers to the process of embedding digital data directly onto multimedia objects such that it can be detected or extracted later. It has three unique advantages.

1. It is imperceptible and does not affect the aesthetic of the digital data.
2. Watermarks become fused with the actual bits of the work, unlike headers they do not get removed when the work is displayed, copied or during format changes.

Based on visibility of digital watermark after embedding, the watermarking process is named as visible watermarking and invisible watermarking. An example of visible watermark is shown in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1. Example of visible watermark

Robustness calls for the watermark to be as strong as possible where the fidelity requirement asks the watermark to be invisible. This is possible with invisible watermarking [3]. An example of an invisible watermark sample is presented in Figure.1.2.

(a)

Figure.1.2. (a) Original Host image, (b) Watermarked Sample

In general, any watermarking system consists of two components;

- a). Embedding and
- b). Extraction

1.1.1 Watermark Embedding: The general idea is to embed a unique mark into a digital image such that it cannot be perceived by the Human Visual System but can be extracted at a later time using the content owner’s secret key to prove ownership. The watermark is a binary image that has been given by the user to the watermarking system for embedding. The host image is first transformed into a domain that facilitates data embedding. The watermark can be embedded generally by adding or multiplying the signal to the host image’s luminance channel, the color channels or both. The embedding unit also has a key which could be either a public or a secret key. The key is used to enforce security, which is prevention of unauthorized parties from manipulating or recovering the watermark. A key is defined as a secret data from the authenticated user used for embedding the watermark image. The authorized user is shared with the key to provide authenticity during decoding operation. A General Watermarking embedding is shown in Figure.1.3.

Figure.1.3. Watermark Embedding Unit

1.1.2 Watermark Extraction: In the extraction stage some watermarking techniques need the original host image for subtracting the watermarked images, such techniques are referred to as “Informed” or private watermarking. Other techniques do not need the original host image but need a secret seed to generate the original watermark for comparison. Such systems are referred to as “blind” watermarking presented. A watermarking system is “semi-blind” if it relies on some data or features derived from the original host image. The simple extraction unit is shown in Figure 1.4.

Figure.1.4. Watermark Decoding Unit

1.1 Applications of Watermarking:

- Owner identification
- Copy protection
- Broadcast monitoring
- Biometric applications
- Data authentication
- Medical applications
- Communication

1.2 Requirements of Watermarking System:

- Complexity
- Security
- Capacity
- Inevitability
- Verification

1.3 Types of watermarking techniques: Watermarking techniques is mainly divided into following four types based on:

- > Type of documents
- > Human perception
- > Application
- > Working Environment

1.3.1 Documents based There is four types of image watermarking based on types of documents on which watermark is embedded known as text, image, audio and video watermarking.

Text watermarking: Text information is embedded into the host.

Image watermarking: Image information is embedded into the host.

Audio watermarking: Audio Information is embedded into the host.

Video watermarking: Video information is embedded into the host.

1.3.2 Human perception Based The image watermarking system ismainly classified in two categories based on human perception, as:

Visible watermarking: In this type of watermarking, the inserted watermark can be easily appearing to the human eyes. This is very simple and easy technique for content authentication but the main drawback of this technique is that it is easily removed from the original host image.

Invisible watermarking: In this type of watermarking technique, the inserted watermark may not have observed by human eyes. Most of the applications of digital image watermarking use this type of watermarking approach.

1.3.3 Application based Source based watermarking:It is used forownership authentication, where unique watermark is embedded to all copies of data. Destination based watermarking: It is used in the application where there is need for tracing buyer for the purpose of illegal reselling.

1.4.4 Working Environment Based Spatial domain watermarking:

This category of watermarking is very simple and also easier to implement. It hides the watermark directly into original data by pixel modification. It has low complexity and high capacity for embedding more number of bits into host data. But these techniques are less resistant to different types of attacks. The techniques use in spatial domain is LSB (Least Significant Bit), ISB (Intermediate Significant Bits) and many more. Frequency domain watermarking: This category of watermarking embeds the watermark in frequency values rather than intensity values. DFT (Discrete Fourier Transform), DCT (Discrete Cosine Transform) and DWT (Discrete Wavelet Transform) are the main methods for transformation in frequency domain watermarking. These are complex but having good imperceptibility and robustness.

2.SYSTEM ANALYSIS

2.1 Discrete Wavelet Transform: Discrete wavelet transform of the image produces multi resolution representation of an image. The multi resolution representation provides a simple framework for interpreting the image information. The DWT analyses the signal at multiple resolution. DWT divides the image into high frequency quadrants and low frequency quadrants. The low frequency quadrant is again split into two more parts of high and low frequencies and this process is repeated until the signal has been entirely decomposed. The single DWT transformed two-dimensional image into four parts: one part is the low frequency of the original image, the top right contains horizontal details of the image, the one bottom left contains vertical details of the original image, the bottom right contains high frequency of the original image. The low frequency coefficients are more robust to embed watermark because it contains more information of the original image. The reconstruct of the original image from the decomposed image is performed by IDWT [34]. The digital wavelet transform is scalable in nature. DWT more frequently used in digital image watermarking because of its excellent spatial localization and multi resolution techniques. The excellent spatial localization property is very convenient to recognize the area in the cover image in which the watermark is embedded efficiently. Figure 2.2 shows the schematic diagram of 2D wavelet transform. By using this figure we can analyse in which way the 2D wavelet transform are performed.

Figure 2.1. Schematic Diagram of 2D Wavelet Transform

2.2 Existing Watermarking System The block diagram of existing watermarking system is shown in figure.2.3 and extraction is shown in figure.2.4

Fig 2.2 Block diagram of Embedding phase of existing system

Fig 2.3 Block diagram of Extraction phase of Existing system

2.3 Disadvantages:

1. Less robust to various attacks like scaling, rotation, and translational attacks.
2. Poor quality of extracted audio watermark.
3. Less Peak signal to noise ratio
4. Less Normalized Cross Correlation.
5. Less robustness

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the proposed system we are going to use both dwt and SVD techniques such that the properties of both the techniques can be obtained.

Fig 3.1 Block diagram of embedding of proposed system

Fig 3.2 Block diagram of Extraction of Proposed system

3.1 Singular value Decomposition: The singular value decomposition (SVD) is a numerical analysis technique based on a theorem of linear algebra that decomposes a rectangular matrix into the product of three matrices: an orthogonal matrix (U), a diagonal matrix (S), and the transpose of an orthogonal matrix (V). It may be considered as a method of transforming correlated data set into uncorrelated one that better explains the various relationships among the original data. Due to the unique features and attractive properties such as stability with little disturbance, SVD has been used in many signal and image processing applications such as image watermarking [4451], image hiding, image compression, and noise reduction. The digital image is also a kind of signal which can be viewed as a matrix. According to the theory, the SVD of a rectangular matrix A of order $m \times n$ is represented mathematically as

$$A = USVT, \quad (2.12)$$

where $UU^T = I_m$ and $VV^T = I_n$; the columns of U are orthonormal eigenvectors of AA^T , the columns of V are orthonormal

vectors of $A^T A$, and S is a diagonal matrix containing the square roots of the eigenvalues from U or V in descending order.

$$\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_r > \lambda_{r+1} = \lambda_{r+2} = \dots = \lambda_n = 0, \quad (2.13)$$

$$A = \sum \lambda_k u_k v_k^T, \quad (2.14)$$

Where u_k and v_k are the k th eigenvector of U and V and λ_k is the k th singular value.

4.SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation results are as follows:

Case 1: Host image: Lena

Size: 512 * 512

Watermark: Audio signal 1

Size: 1 * 25000

dio						
3						

(e)
Figure 4.1 (a) Original color image (b) Green plane (c) Red Plane (d) Blue plane (e) Watermarked image

(a)
Figure 4.2 (a) Original audio watermark (b) Extracted audio Watermark

Table.4.1 Performance Metrics for Lena watermarked image

Case	PSNR			SPCC		
	_R	_G	_B	_R	_G	_B
Lena with Audio 1	24.8036	24.8068	24.8002	0.8140	0.8190	0.8177
Lena with Audio 2	24.6289	24.6294	24.6367	0.8296	0.8258	0.8322
Lena with Audio 3	25.8277	25.8216	25.8246	0.8877	0.8897	0.8903

Table 4.2 Performance metrics for Watermark image

Case	PSNR			SSIM		
	_R	_G	_B	_R	_G	_B
Lena with Audio 1	35.7086	35.4756	36.1835	0.9043	0.9070	0.8942
Lena with Audio 2	29.0618	28.8140	29.5245	0.8915	0.8941	0.8813
Lena with Audio	33.7495	33.5078	34.2197	0.8309	0.8336	0.8208

5. Conclusion and Future Scope

5.1 Conclusion

The digital revolution, the explosion of communication networks, and the increasingly growing passion of the general public for new information technologies lead to exponential growth of multimedia document traffic (image, text, audio, video, etc.). This phenomenon is now so important that insuring protection and control of the exchanged data has become a major issue. Indeed, from their digital nature, multimedia documents can be duplicated, modified, transformed, and diffused very easily. In this

context, it is important to develop systems for copyright protection, protection against duplication, and authentication of content. Watermarking is one of the best solutions reinforcing the security of multimedia documents. In this thesis a framework for semi-blind digital image watermarking is illustrated. This is a hybrid framework, developed by combining multiple preliminaries such as Discrete Wavelet Transform, and Singular Value Decomposition.

5.2 Future Scope

The developed watermarking framework of this thesis can be extended in future through so many ways. Some of them are illustrated here.

- Since the watermarking system is more flexible for image transformation approaches like DWT, SVD etc., it can be extended through the further advanced transform techniques such as Contourlet Transform (CT) and Non-Subsampled Contour Transform (NSCT) which makes the system more resilient to various attacks.
- When there is an extension of image watermarking through digital signature embedding like concepts the computational complexity will raise. To reduce the computational complexity, a band selection procedure can be accomplished in which the limited

number of bands of host and watermark images is processed. This band selection procedure makes the system less complex and also more robust.